

The Big Five Personality Traits and Family Relationship Quality among Married Couples: The Mediating Role of Emotional Stress and Marital Depression

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Abstract: The present study aimed to examine the influence of the Big Five personality traits on the quality of family relationships among married couples, with particular attention to the mediating roles of emotional stress and marital depression. It also explored potential gender differences across the study variables. The sample comprised 433 married individuals (145 males and 288 females) residing in the United Arab Emirates. Four standardized instruments were employed: the Big Five Personality Traits Scale, the Family Relationship Quality Scale, the Marital Emotional Stress Scale, and the Marital Depression Scale. The results revealed significant associations between the Big Five personality traits and marital relationship quality. Neuroticism demonstrated a negative relationship with relationship quality, whereas extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were positively associated. Moreover, emotional stress and marital depression partially mediated the relationship between personality traits and marital relationship quality, indicating that the direct effects of personality traits were reduced when these mediating variables were considered. Additionally, no significant gender differences were found in relationship quality; however, females reported higher levels of emotional stress and marital depression compared to males.

Keywords: Big Five Personality dimensions; Quality of Family Relationships; Emotional Stress; Marital Depression; Relationship Satisfaction; Personality influences on relationship outcomes; Marital Adjustment; Psychological Well-being; Couples' Mental Health.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality Family stability is considered one of the fundamental pillars of mental health for family members (Cooklin, Dinh, Strazdins, Westrupp, Leach, & Nicholson, 2016). Mutual understanding and compatibility form the core of healthy family relationships, significantly influencing the psychological and emotional balance of spouses (Melhem, Hayajneh, Irshaid, Badarneh, & Anbar, 2020). Accordingly, researchers in psychology have paid considerable attention to understanding and assessing the factors affecting family relationships, among which personality traits hold a central role.

The concept of personality is considered one of the most intricate and multifaceted ideas within the field of psychology. Individual personalities are distinct, and people's behaviors or verbal expressions are derived from their overall personality framework (Bergner, 2020), as Roberts and Yoon (2022) pointed out. A person's personality greatly impacts their family relationships, with marriage being a significant life stage that significantly affects the quality of family interactions, depending on each spouse's personality characteristics (Moynihan, 2017).

Family stability is threatened by one of the psychological challenges, namely emotional stress (Strizhitskaya, Petrash, Savenysheva, Murtazina, & Golovey, 2019), with persistent partner tension commonly causing marital depression (Rao, 2017). Spousal relationships are influenced by personality traits in terms of adjustment, levels of support, and interaction (Mousavi, 2017). The insights highlighted raise critical concerns about the link between spouses' personality traits and the psychological risk factors that threaten emotional and psychological stability in marriage.

This study aims to investigate how the Big Five personality traits affect the quality of family relationships in married couples, with a specific emphasis on the roles played by emotional stress and marital depression. The study seeks to gain a more thorough and detailed knowledge of the psychological factors affecting family relationship quality, thereby aiding in the creation of preventive and counselling strategies that foster stability and support within family life.

Marital and familial relationships are often a primary source of emotional support for many people. Their success encourages family adaptation and mental well-being (Qadir, Khalid, Haqqani, & Medhin, 2013). These relationships are influenced by a variety of factors, such as personality characteristics, psychological forces, and levels of emotional comprehension (Gottman & Silver, 2012). The Big Five personality traits model has been established as a theoretical framework offering valuable insights into understanding individual differences that impact family interactions, emotional understanding, and marital satisfaction (Sayehmiri et al., 2020).

In another area, marital depression is a considerable psychological factor that reduces the quality of marital life (Goldfarb & Trudel, 2019). Marital dissolution and separation are further increased by emotional stress, resulting in a significant negative impact on family well-being (Han, Park, Kim, Kim, & Park, 2014). Marital satisfaction is closely associated with certain personality traits, which can predict the quality of relationships and psychological stability within families. The Big Five personality traits have been demonstrated to forecast couples' inclinations toward adjusting to married life (Sayehmiri, Kareem, Abdi, Dalvand, & Gheshlagh, 2020).

The importance of this study lies in filling a clear research void by investigating how the Big Five personality traits affect the quality of family relationships among married couples, specifically through the mediating roles of emotional stress and marital depression. The study aims to gain a more comprehensive and in-depth insight into the psychological factors that influence the quality of family relationships, ultimately improving therapy techniques used in family counseling.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Divergent views exist regarding the concept of personality, primarily because of varying assumptions about human nature. To some, personality consists of an interconnected system of mental, physical, emotional, and social characteristics that define the individual (Mayer, 2017). According to Staats (1980), it is essentially consistent patterns of behavior that occur across various settings and can be anticipated. According to Durbin and Hicks (2014), personality is an individual's distinct arrangement of thoughts, values, and attitudes, which are formed through social interaction. According to Propat and Corr (2015), the integrated organisation is seen because of the interaction between biological, social, and cultural factors.

Several theories have sought to explain personality. According to psychoanalytic theory, personality is formed through the interaction of three systems: the id, which is instinctive and unconscious; the ego, which is the realistic mediator; and the superego, which serves as the moral conscience (Kohut & Seitz, 2018). The ego achieves a state of psychological adjustment when it strikes a balance between two opposing forces, whereas an imbalance in this equilibrium can result in personality disturbance (Adas & Tawq, 1995).

The behavioral perspective emphasizes the part environmental experiences play in forming personality, viewing it as acquired patterns of behavior and emotions developed through reinforcement and punishment (Corey, 2005). According to Mahfoudh et al. (2025), personality develops through a process of interactive learning, where individual responses are re-shaped within environments that are rich in feedback and support. Helali, Bani-Rshaid, Al-Lawama, Alromaih, and Al-Osail (2024) note that personality traits are intertwined with cultural contexts rather than being separate entities, highlighting a reciprocal relationship between individual and societal factors in personality development. Trait theory proposes that personality comprises both general and specific characteristics—some primary or secondary, others fundamental—resulting in observable attributes such as cheerfulness or introversion. These traits may be acquired or inherited, and are relatively stable, thus allowing for behavioral predictability (Adas & Tawq, 1995).

Several models have been proposed to conceptualise the Big Five factors of personality. Cattell's model classified traits as either unique or common, and recognised three categories: ability traits, temperament traits, and dynamic traits (Cattell, Eber, & Tatsuoka, 1970). Eysenck categorized personality into three aspects: neuroticism versus emotional stability, extraversion versus introversion, and psychoticism versus non-psychotic tendencies. According to Eysenck, individuals with high levels of psychoticism often experience social isolation and a lack of empathy (Eysenck & Eysenck, 1987). Costa and McCrae subsequently introduced the widely recognised Five-Factor Model, which includes neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness relatively stable dispositions that define the overall personality pattern (Naydenova, Lounsbury, Levy, & Kim, 2012).

The Big Five model has garnered significant academic interest. According to Ahmetoglu and Chamorro-Premuzic (2012), personality is comprised of five core traits that predict habitual actions across various settings, and play a significant role in areas such as employment, partner choice, and post-divorce healing. According to Salhi, Ait, and Sharifi (2018), the Big Five personality traits are linked to success or failure in life, with neuroticism and conscientiousness having a notable impact on life history and environmental interactions. Additionally, Wayne, Musisca, and Fleeson (2004) found that extraversion plays a key role in family conflict and adjustment, with extraversion facilitating role transitions and reducing conflict, and neuroticism exacerbating family tensions. Byng-Hall (2008) stressed that effective interactions between married couples depend on mutual compatibility and flexibility in order to maintain family stability and adaptability.

Continuous interactions among family members result in their relationships, which are formed by the level and type of reciprocal communication (Ewertzon, Lutzen, Svensson, & Andershed, 2010). A supportive marital environment promotes healthy psychological development, whereas negative relationships lead to maladjustment and weakened trust (Corey, 2012). Families marked by turmoil and conflict tend to exhibit lower levels of adaptation, whereas stable families provide members with opportunities for growth and prepare them for social integration (South, Doss, & Christensen, 2010). Successful marriages are built on effective communication between spouses, but poor communication can worsen conflicts (Knapp, Sandberg, Novak, & Larson, 2015). Sustaining positive family relationships necessitates a mutual exchange of emotions, empathy, and affection to guarantee optimal family functioning (Byng-Hall, 2008).

Central to mental health is the concept of quality of life, which includes happiness, social well-being, and interpersonal relationships, and serves as a key indicator of successful integration into daily life and active participation in activities (Bani-Rshaid, Al-Serhan, & Jaradat, 2019). Family stability relies on having a satisfying marriage and a positive relationship with one's spouse (Ahmad & Zaki, 2022). Family relationship quality, as stated by Sillars, Canary, and Tafoya (2003), relies heavily on positive interaction, emotional support, effective communication, and conflict management. Bluemke, Grevenstein, Schweitzer, and Aguilar-Raab (2019) described it as including a couple's assessment of their marriage and their overall feeling of happiness and contentment. Research by Thomas, Liu, and Umberson in 2017 found a strong correlation between marital quality and overall well-being, highlighting that individuals in troubled marriages tend to experience increased levels of depression and poor health, whereas those in fulfilling marriages typically receive emotional support and have a stress buffer. Marital continuity and quality are thought to be influenced by balancing rewards and costs, with both partners aiming for equal status and psychological fulfillment, according to social exchange theory (Sharifian, Saffarinia, & Alizadeh, 2020). Additionally, congruence theory holds that shared values and interests are crucial for a fulfilling marriage (Hudson & Fraley, 2014), and similarity in the partners' characteristics tends to result in higher relationship satisfaction (Sayehmiri, Kareem, Abdi, Dalvand, & Gheshlagh, 2020).

Family conflict is linked to emotional stress, which creates persistent tension in couples' relationships, characterized by feelings of distress and strain (Neff & Broady, 2011). Research has shown that emotional stress can drain couples' emotional and psychological reserves (Falconier, Nussbeck, Bodenmann, Schneider, and Bradbury, 2015). Couples experiencing high stress, as identified by Han, Park, Kim, Kim, and Park (2014), often struggle to offer mutual support, resulting in weakened emotional bonds and diminished intimacy, a link to marital dissolution also established by Birditt, Wan, Orbuch, and Antonucci (2017). Karney and Bradbury (1995) noted that obsessive tendencies are detrimental to marital quality, often leading to increased emotional instability and negative emotions in highly compulsive individuals, which can intensify conflict and lower marital stability.

Humans, as inherently social beings, require positive interactions to maintain mental health and a sense of belonging. Negative interactions, conversely, may produce isolation and alienation (Bani-Rshaid, Hussein, Ababneh, & Khasawneh, 2023). Bani-Irshid and Bani-Rshaid (2022) stressed the importance of psychological factors in explaining individual behavioral differences, noting that anxiety negatively affects both functional and psychological performance in contexts

requiring effective interaction. Within marital life, depression frequently arises as a psychological outcome of chronic stress, as repeated negative experiences of frustration and hopelessness render couples more vulnerable to depression (Abu Zaid, 2023). The effects of depression extend beyond individual well-being to negatively influence marital satisfaction and overall relationship quality (Goldfarb & Trudel, 2019).

The Big Five traits have been thoroughly researched as a comprehensive framework for grasping individual differences in social and emotional interactions. Research has consistently shown a close relationship between them and a spouse's overall satisfaction with the marriage. Claxton, O'Rourke, Smith, and DeLongis (2012) discovered that marital satisfaction was linked with positive outcomes for extraversion, openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness, but was negatively correlated with neuroticism. According to Ranjana (2015), neuroticism has a strong association with decreased cohesion, autonomy, and recreational orientation, and is positively linked with conflict. Researchers such as Sayehmiri et al. (2020) have found that people with high neuroticism have lower marital satisfaction, whereas those with strong conscientiousness report higher satisfaction. Brudek et al. (2018) discovered that extraversion, openness, and conscientiousness are positive marital satisfaction factors for older couples, aged 60–75, whereas high neuroticism contributes to lower satisfaction. Schaffhuser et al. (2014) also found neuroticism is negatively associated with marital satisfaction, whereas agreeableness and conscientiousness are positively linked. Taggart et al. (2019) observed that individuals with lower neuroticism and conscientiousness reported a stronger relationship between conflict resolution and marital satisfaction. Research by Najarpourian et al. in 2012 found that people with low neuroticism and high levels of both extraversion and conscientiousness appeared to have the highest level of marital satisfaction, whereas those who scored high on neuroticism reported the lowest.

Research further indicates that emotional stress represents a state of emotional exhaustion resulting from repeated pressures, which weakens marital quality. Ouseph and Bance (2022) found that marital stress was negatively correlated with relationship quality and satisfaction. Zanganeh, Yousefi, and Karimi (2021) demonstrated that openness and agreeableness predict stress and emotional burnout in couples, with agreeableness positively predicting marital burnout and openness negatively predicting it. Other traits were not statistically significant. Goldfarb and Trudel (2019) reported a robust cross-sectional association between depression and marital quality, noting that high depressive symptoms correspond with lower marital quality and that unsatisfying marriages increase the risk of major depression. Finkel, Slotter, Luchies, Walton, and Gross (2013) conducted one of the few studies integrating personality traits and psychological stressors into a single explanatory model, revealing that the negative effects of neuroticism on marital relationships are amplified under conditions of high emotional stress.

Although existing literature underscores the importance of the Big Five in explaining patterns of interaction and family relationships, a notable gap remains in studies incorporating these traits within integrative explanatory models that include mediating psychological variables such as emotional stress and marital depression. Accordingly, the present study seeks to address this gap by testing an explanatory model that integrates personality structure with psychological stressors to better understand marital relationship quality. This effort aims to inform the development of culturally relevant and practically effective counseling interventions.

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The quality of family relationships is widely believed to be influenced by the Big Five personality traits. While much of the existing research has focused on the impact of each trait separately, less attention has been given to potential mediating factors such as marital depression and emotional stress that may play a central role in shaping marital dynamics. This study aims to explore how the Big Five traits are related to the quality of family relationships, while also considering the contribution of emotional stress and marital depression. In addition, the analysis considers gender differences and key demographic characteristics.

Based on this, the study raises the following research questions:

1. What are the correlations between the Big Five personality traits, relationship quality, emotional stress, and marital depression?
2. To what extent do the Big Five personality traits influence the quality of marital relationships?
3. Do emotional stress and marital depression significantly predict the quality of marital relationships?
4. Are there statistically significant gender differences in emotional stress, marital depression, and marital relationship quality?

4. METHOD

Participants

The study population consisted of all married individuals residing in the Emirate of Abu Dhabi. The final sample comprised 433 married participants, including 145 males and 288 females, who were selected using a random sampling technique. The survey was conducted after informing participants that their involvement was voluntary, and assurances were provided regarding the confidentiality of their responses.

5. INSTRUMENTATION

four scales were used in this study

1. The Big Five Personality Traits Scale: The study utilized the Big Five Personality Traits Scale developed by John, Donahue, and Kentle (1991) and adapted by Jaradat and Abu Ghazal (2014) to suit the Arab cultural context. The scale consists of 44 items distributed across five dimensions: Neuroticism (items 1–8), Extraversion (items 9–16), Openness to Experience (items 17–26), Agreeableness (items 27–35), and Conscientiousness (items 36–44). Both the original scale and its adapted version have been validated in previous studies (John, Donahue, & Kentle, 1991; Jaradat & Abu Ghazal, 2014), demonstrating acceptable levels of validity and reliability.

Construct Validity: The scale was administered to a pilot sample of 36 participants to verify its validity. Correlation coefficients for each item with the total score were calculated, and the scores ranged from 0.64 to 0.79.

Inventory Reliability: The internal consistency of The Big Five Personality Traits Scale Inventory was computed by using the Cronbach Alpha on the responses of the pilot sample, with coefficients ranging from 0.71 to 0.76, indicating satisfactory reliability.

2. Family Relationship Quality Scale: The researchers developed a Family Relationship Quality Scale based on previous published measures (Grevenstein, Bluemke, Schweitzer, & Aguilar-Raab, 2019; Sitota & Tefera, 2022; Fok, Allen, Henry, & Team, 2014). The scale consists of 10 items answered using a five-point Likert scale: "Strongly Disagree" (1), "Disagree" (2), "Neutral" (3), "Agree" (4), and "Strongly Agree" (5). The scale includes three dimensions: family communication effectiveness, support and empathy, family belonging and cohesion. Scores were categorized as follows: low (1.00–2.33), medium (2.34–3.67), and high (3.68–5.00). Further classification included: very low (1.00–1.80), low (1.81–2.60), medium (2.61–3.40), high (3.41–4.20), and very high (4.21–5.00).

Construct Validity: The Cronbach's alpha was calculated using a pilot sample of 36 participants, yielding a high reliability coefficient of 0.88.

Inventory Reliability: Cronbach's alpha was calculated using a pilot sample of 36 participants, yielding a high reliability coefficient of 0.88.

3. Marital Emotional Stress Scale: The researchers developed a brief Marital Emotional Stress Scale based on previous theoretical models of marital stress (Bodenmann, 2005; Hashemi & Homayuni, 2017; Birditt, Wan, Orbuch, & Antonucci, 2017; Manalel, Birditt, Orbuch, & Antonucci, 2019). The scale comprises 10 items rated on a five-point Likert scale.

The scale measures four dimensions: internal emotional pressure, stress arising from responsibilities, and feelings of emotional exhaustion and isolation.

Construct Validity: To ensure construct validity, the scale was piloted on a sample of 36 individuals from outside the main study sample. Item-total correlations ranged from 0.74 to 0.94, indicating strong validity.

Inventory Reliability: Cronbach's alpha was calculated based on the pilot sample, yielding a high reliability coefficient of 0.84, confirming the strength of the scale for measuring marital emotional stress.

4. Marital Depression Scale: The Marital Depression Scale was developed based on conceptualizations of marital depression (Goldfarb & Trudel, 2019; Woods, Priest, Signs, & Maier, 2019; Ozguç & Tanrıverdi, 2018; Whisman, 2001). The scale comprises 10 items rated on a five-point Likert scale. It measures three dimensions: marital sadness and frustration, emotional indifference and distancing toward the partner, and decreased energy and willingness to interact or improve the relationship.

Construct Validity: Construct validity was examined with a pilot sample of 36 individuals from outside the main study sample. Item-total correlations ranged from 0.72 to 0.89, indicating strong validity.

Inventory Reliability: Cronbach's alpha coefficient, calculated on the pilot sample, was 0.83, confirming the reliability of the scale for assessing marital depression.

6. RESULTS

To answer the first question “What are the correlations between the Big Five personality traits, relationship quality, emotional stress, and marital depression?” Correlation coefficients were calculated between the Big Five personality traits (Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness to Experience, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness) and marital quality, emotional stress, and marital depression. as illustrated in table 1.

Table 1: Correlation Coefficients

Variable	Relationship Quality	Emotional Stress	Marital Depression
Neuroticism	-0.42**	0.47**	0.44**
Extraversion	0.39**	-0.31**	-0.28**
Openness to Experience	0.31**	-0.22**	-0.25**
Agreeableness	0.36**	-0.29**	-0.30**
Conscientiousness	0.46**	-0.34**	-0.32**

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

The table above shows significant correlations between the Big Five personality factors and relationship quality. Neuroticism was negatively associated with relationship quality, while the other four traits were positively associated with relationship quality. Nervous distress and marital depression were also positively associated with neuroticism and negatively associated with other traits.

To answer the second question, “To what extent do the Big Five personality traits affect the quality of marital relationships?”, a multiple regression analysis was conducted using personality traits as independent variables and the quality of marital relationships as the dependent variable, as shown in Table (2).

Table 2: Multiple Regression Results

Predictor	β (Beta)	t	Sig. (p)
Neuroticism	-0.29	-6.45	0.000
Extraversion	0.18	3.65	0.001
Openness to Experience	0.11	2.21	0.028
Agreeableness	0.15	3.11	0.002
Conscientiousness	0.22	4.71	0.000
Model Summary	$R^2 = 0.32$	$F(5,427) = 28.67$	$p < 0.001$

The model explained 32% of the variance in relationship quality. Neuroticism was the strongest negative predictor, while conscientiousness and extraversion were the strongest positive predictors. Openness and agreeableness also contributed significantly.

To answer the question, “Do emotional stress and marital depression significantly predict the quality of marital relationships?”, Mediation Analysis was used to demonstrate the mediating role of both emotional stress and marital depression in the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and marital relationship quality. Path analysis (mediation analysis) was conducted to estimate the direct, indirect and total effects, as shown in Table (3).

Table 3: Mediation Analysis Results

Path	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Significance
Neuroticism → Relationship Quality	-0.22	-0.19	-0.41	0.001**
Conscientiousness → Relationship Quality	0.20	0.14	0.34	0.001**
Extraversion → Relationship Quality	0.24	0.07	0.31	0.01*
Agreeableness & Openness → Relationship Quality	0.18	0.05	0.23	0.05*

Model fit indices: $\chi^2/df = 2.41$, CFI = 0.94, RMSEA = 0.051

The table above shows that emotional stress and marital depression played a partial mediating role in the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and the quality of family relationships. The effects of neuroticism and conscientiousness played a clear mediating role.

To answer the question, “Are there statistically significant gender differences in emotional stress, marital depression, and marital relationship quality?”, The independent t-test was used to study the differences between males and females in emotional stress, marital depression, and marital relationship quality, with the aim of determining whether there are statistically significant differences resulting from the effect of gender, as shown in Table (4).

Table 4: Gender Differences

Variable	Males (M ± SD)	Females (M ± SD)	t	Sig. (p)
Relationship Quality	3.74 ± 0.59	3.78 ± 0.57	-0.65	0.51
Emotional Stress	2.73 ± 0.64	2.96 ± 0.68	-2.45	0.015*
Marital Depression	2.61 ± 0.66	2.81 ± 0.72	-2.18	0.031*

* $p < 0.05$

Table (4) shows no statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) attributable to the effect of gender on relationship quality. However, there were gender differences favoring females in emotional stress and marital depression compared to males.

7. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to examine the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and marital relationship quality among married individuals, while testing the mediating role of emotional stress and marital depression. It also sought to identify gender differences in these variables.

The results indicated significant associations between all Big Five personality traits and marital quality. Neuroticism was negatively associated with marital quality, while extroversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were positively associated with marital quality. These findings are consistent with Clacton et al.'s (2012) study, who confirmed that neuroticism is negatively associated with marital satisfaction, while extroversion and conscientiousness positively predicted relationship quality. Similarly, Nagarpurian et al. (2012) found that couples low in neuroticism and high in conscientiousness reported the highest levels of marital satisfaction. However, these findings differ somewhat from Ranjana's (2015) study.

The findings indicated that emotional stress and marital depression partially mediated the relationship between personality traits and marital relationship quality. The direct effects of personality traits on relationship quality were reduced when these mediators were included in the model. This result is consistent with Finkel et al. (2013), who indicated that the negative impact of neuroticism on marital quality intensifies under high emotional stress. It also aligns with Zanganeh, Yousefi, & Karimi (2021), who found that personality traits, particularly openness and agreeableness, affect levels of emotional stress and marital burnout among couples. Notably, neuroticism emerged as the most influential trait in increasing emotional stress and marital depression, consistent with Han et al. (2014), who emphasized the detrimental effect of neuroticism on marital quality due to emotional instability.

The study found no significant gender differences in marital relationship quality, which aligns with Knapp, Sandberg, Novak, & Larson (2015), suggesting that marital quality depends more on interaction patterns rather than gender. However, females reported significantly higher levels of emotional stress and marital depression than males. This finding is consistent with Birditt, Wan, Orbuch, & Antonucci (2017), who argued that women are more vulnerable to emotional stress in marital contexts due to the nature of social and cultural roles.

These findings support the hypothesis that personality traits constitute a foundational factor for understanding marital relationship quality, and that psychological mediators such as emotional stress and marital depression play a critical role in explaining this relationship. They underscore the importance of developing targeted marital interventions to improve emotional coping skills, especially for couples with high levels of neuroticism.

From a practical perspective, these findings offer significant implications for marital counseling and intervention programs. They highlight the importance of designing counseling initiatives that focus on enhancing couples' skills in managing stress and resolving conflicts effectively. Furthermore, the results support the development of personality-based assessment tools

that can help identify the strengths and weaknesses within marital relationships, thereby enabling counselors to tailor their approaches to the specific needs of each couple. Ultimately, interventions that integrate an understanding of personality traits as influential factors in relationship dynamics are likely to be more effective in promoting marital satisfaction, emotional well-being, and long-term relational stability.

8. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Limitations: Despite the study's contributions, there are limitations. The study sample was limited to the Abu Dhabi region, limiting the generalizability of the findings. It is recommended that future studies include diverse samples from multiple spatial and cultural contexts, as well as use multiple methods such as interviews, to further deepen understanding of the associations between personality traits and marital quality.

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